

Army Explosives and Ammunitions - Robbery and Recovery

Quote

“In 2018, the Defence Minister said to the Parliament inquiry Commission that he was unaware of the discrepancy between the material reported to have been recovered by the army and what has not yet appeared. “If I was informed? No, I was not informed. Because whoever investigated probably thought it would be a secret of justice”, there are explosives, grenades, tear grenades and a decompression trigger yet to be found, contrary to what the Army announced.

In 2020 the ex Defence Minister, changing his declarations admitted to the Public Prosecutor that he had known that the weapons stolen from Tancos' storerooms were found after a fake call saying where they were.”

“Today we live in an Era of Responsibility”

Alain Etchegoyen means that we usually use the word “responsibility” under different concepts, in a new way of thinking, acting, and implementing one moral and personal responsibility, and all the others uses of this word underlies on this.

When we look at the meaning of corruption, we find synonyms like “decomposition”, adulteration. Is in its way that we can reprove any mal function of a public service or of the responsible – this is the sense of corruption that any citizen has.

In a political way, the concept of corruption emerges from an “informal political system” that takes flexible decisions instead of going on the formal and strict way imposed by administrative rules. (Friedrich, 1966 pag. 85; Scott, 1972 pag.2).

Corruption appears when an ethical senses is absent from the public system. The opportunities and incentive for corruption comes when there are privatizations - (The World Bank, Viewpoint, Note nº 74-75, April 1996).

Also when power and economy become together in a time when the opportunity to accede to the power is an open way to personal wealth the corruption appears - (Della Porta & Pizzorno, 1996). .

The external financial help, more than helping the public reforms, takes the way to sustain the corrupted political elites - (Ziegler, 1996 pag. 21).

The corruption is seen an endemic phenomena, a kind of super system that becomes much more effective that the one that legitimates the power- (Deysine, 1980 pag.453; Werlin, 1994 pag. 548-9; Della Porta & Mény, 1995 pag. 12).

The called private appropriation of the public belongings represents the State corruption - (Mény, 1994 pag16)

Political approach - Public Integrity in the Public Interest

The conception of Power – “Latin origin potere” can be applied to a person or group having great influence, force or authority, this last meaning the power or right to give commands, enforce obedience, take action or make final decisions meaning also a jurisdiction.

In a “bad way “a constant striving for power or authority in politics is a desire to find a source of a superior power upon one relies.

In History we have a large number of authors and essays about the theory of power and all gives the correlation with authoritarianism. The authoritarians can be found at any level of intelligence, socially agreeable and well- adjusted, hard working and reliable. vide - Horace B. English

We will try to establish an actual link between POWER – and Public Integrity in the Public Interest following the distortions of its concept and functions in an democratic society where the exercise of the Power is legitimated by the People that elects someone to rule in their collective benefit and use the influence and authority to give welfare, development. A fair exercise of authority is the motivation of the electors.

Distortions of power are believed to conduct to a distortions of peoples rule and government making the legal framework of “abuse of power” an inconsistent and with obvious useless.

In this reflections we will try to demonstrate with real facts that a Democracy can assume a authoritarianism shape and the “Public” can turn victims of their own choice.

THE CIVIL SOCIETY is organized accordingly their Constitution of the Nation.

The sovereign Nation is organized and implemented by the Constitution that is the guarantee of the effectiveness of civil rights and liberties in order to achieve the full Democratic State through the economically, socially, cultural promoting peoples participation.

So the State has functions and duties subordinated to the public rights and duties. No restraint of the main rights is possible unless it offends this main pillar of public organization.

The citizens are protected by the State in several ways:

- The guaranty of access to Justice through the Courts;
- The right to resist to any order that offends the public rights, liberties and constitutional guarantees;
- The protection of the citizens by the responsibility of the public servants or political leaders of the State;
- The instruments to assure their liberties – freedom – privacy of their home and mail – access to informatics databases where a person has a file – to have a family – to be able to express their opinions – about to be or not religious – to learn, to teach and the access to culture - to move around the territory and go out of it – to have public meetings and make legal associations – to choose their work - .
- The rights that emerge from these liberties become effective as – to have a work – to have quality in services and goods – to have their own property – to have protection in health – to have a home – to have a good quality way of life ecologically protected - to have protection for the family, young , elderly and handicapped people – to learn, to access to culture, sports practice :

So the State has to be organized to achieve all these goals defining policies in the specific ways – through the Government and in national policies, for instance agricultural, economical, industrial, and commercial. Also is organized to get revenues to pay the structures through a tax policy.

To act there is the political power that belongs to the people – the PUBLIC – and is exercised accordingly the Constitution of the Country.

Mainly and accordingly with the political democratic system of a Country we can define, in General Four main sovereign entities: The President of the Republic – Parliament – the Govern and the Courts, each one independent from the others in a question of balance to assure the Democratic balance and avoid the takeover of POWER.

These entities have a Constitutional control and are organized in order to prevent malfunctions.

The defined and undefined groups

As Political parties are entitled to propose different options to the Public – the electors – and are legal associations with a special legislation. Their objective of a political party is to become in a majority of votes in the elections and to provide candidates to the independent Entities – The President of the Republic – Parliament – the Govern and the Courts.

- Here we can say that the integrity problems begun. The fund raising and grey investments and connections of political parties in order to gain control of the media to reach the electors and to benefit themselves for the time lost in political activities – while not elected.

Most of their leaders are professionals on political campaigns and are supported by others that have no time because have another job – So we call professional politics career -.

- Each political party is organized and is ruled by its bylaw. Is a defined Group to the Public. Nowadays we find political strategies that involve negotiations and conversations between political parties, in special when they are willing to run a coalition Government or Parliament.

So mutual agreements that involves different purposes reaching objectives from one and the other party, makes political life a bargaining time job between politicians “of line” without Public acknowledgement and without transparency – only the leaders are supposed to decide to forward on giving what the other party wants.

- Also in the same party, people are free to their opinion and point of view and there are also elections for the leadership of that political association. At this moment is relevant – not the Public – the friends support, witch can have different origins – religious, members of same secret societies, economical, or just social and personal.

- All this points makes the political association an undefined group to the Public.

The conflict individual interest and public interest

When a political elected leader is after elections to become President of Republic, Member of Parliament or to organize a government there is several decisions factors at the time:

- The public commitment of the political party to the electors;

- The nominations or invitations inside the party accordingly the internal tendency;

- The personal commitments with the sponsors of the public campaigns;

- The negotiations with other party in the case of a coalition or just a simple voting majority in Parliament.

The decisions are entitled to reach the satisfaction of private commitments and appear as satisfaction of Public commitments.

The public servants and the parties

Now a day everybody is aware that to be a public servant is the corollary of a safety in the job, in the salary and in retirement.

The public sector becomes more attractive than the private sector where unemployment, unpaid salaries, ordinary situations with the world financial crisis. Also a career is very difficult while the public servant has a pre crisis legislation that allows a evolution in the career either economical but also in progression of the rank.

Most of invitations to govern are made to public servants depending from the affiliation and position on the party tendency and even in examinations for progression on the career the results are many time reviewed according that same criteria.

In is daily job the public servant not compromised hasn't any incentive to do a good work with quality and commitment. The others depending from the political party, are very reliable according the instructions and ignoring a equal public treatment in their job.

The decision and authority

And the Power that comes up side down in several partial delegations becomes centralized at one undetermined point that can be for instance in the chief of cabinet of the Minister – in the secretary of State, in the General Director – in the vice Director – in the department chief or in extreme and strict cases just in the simple inspector.

Our laws most of them are enough good and theoretically perfect. Our democratic system is all well organized and the Peoples Liberties and Rights are in the Law.

However the dispersion of power having different factors and sources can lead to an authoritarianism kind of “new democracy” where the Law exist but is ineffective.

To reform is not a necessity in some cases. The political will is very questionable because all the whole system exists but does not work because it serves the individual purposes and who has the power has legal impunity and the retaliation of any democratic group or person is fatal.

The attitude of the public is very like it is in a non democratic political system. The oppression and unsafe way of living is a form that produces social distortions like alcohol, drugs, suicide and necessary goes in the end to corruption in different scales and measures, as a way to survive in “democracy”.

Controlling

There are many theories that based on these concepts try to analyze corruption and discovering control mechanisms.

The typology of White, Grey and Black corruption is one method for reach a control - Arnold Heidenheimer.

The White corruption is based on personal of family relations. Is the one more difficult to control.

The grey corruption is the one that having a standard conduct as a model, gives a different sense to that model as it happens with public servants - Friedrich, 1966 pag.74; Jos, 1993 pag. 359-6; Gardiner, 1993 pag. 111-6; Kjellberg, 1995 pag. 342).

The Black corruption is the one legally defined and punished. “ When a civil servant by himself or by a third party, with his consent or agreement, asks or accepts for himself or for a third party, without being due, an patrimonial or non patrimonial advantage ,

or its promise, having as a payment of act or omission contrary to his duties, commits corruption, even if it is only an attempt.

Spreads Concepts of related phenomena

Fraud – When someone uses a false document, fact or reason to get a personal or third party advantage;

- Bribe – When someone try to convince other, by a gift or with the promise of a personal or patrimonial advantage to practice acts;

- Personal favours - When someone totally or partially stop, frustrate or elude any kind of legal activity with the intention that other person is punished;

- Concussion – When someone with power takes an advantage from a victim error receiving much more than is due;

- Abuse of power – The public servant that out of his powers violate his duties to obtain for himself or third party a patrimonial or personal advantage;

- Exchange of favours – When two persons commits acts in order to take personal or patrimonial advantage for each other;

Undefined Concepts

The advantages of any non-moral activity following Arnold Heidenheimer concepts of White – Grey or Black corruption becomes undefined when in a non-touchable result or advantage. The result of the illicit or reprovved conduct can only exist as a promise or with a future effectiveness. Although is a distortion.

The concept of Transparency – acting in a public way without any moral or legal censorship is the way to define “ a contrario sensu” those undefined situation. The absence of Transparency is the presence of an illegal or immoral behaviour.

Psychological motivation for corruption

Conceptualizing, analyzing and studying corruption must also be a study about the psychological behaviour of the agent.

The distortion can have different sources:

- Social ones- related with historical habits or practices;
- Financial ones – the need of money to survive on normal or abnormal ways or the greed to get ways to power;
- Personal ones – Family problems, drug or alcohol addiction, “illnesses”.

Monitoring motivations

There are many ways for monitoring motivations especially with written psychological tests.

Most of decision takers despite their public known integrity should be submitted to tests and monitoring preventing distortions. A divorce, the death of a relative, an sudden illness are unpredictable and can affect behaviours, conducting to anti social practices, namely corruption “ as a revenge” from society.

If military and police forces have those psychological tests, because they use the power of guns, also the power of decision should equally be protected.

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